

iImagine

First Innovation Management and Exploitation Plan

iImagine Deliverable D2.2

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Abstract

This deliverable provides an overview on how project result and key exploitable results will be managed. Moreover, a plan for the stakeholder analysis and exploitation is also presented in the document. Finally the document provides with an overview of the steps that T2.1 will carry out during the next 15 months.

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Introduction

iImagine has the overall objective to deploy, operate, validate, and promote a dedicated iImagine AI framework and platform. The platform connected to the EOSC and AI4EU provides researchers in aquatic sciences with open access to a diverse portfolio of AI-based image analysis services and image repositories from multiple RIs. These services and repositories are of relevance to the overarching theme of 'Healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters'.

The project concept revolves around three main working blocks:

- A common **iImagine AI framework and computing platform** will be configured facilitating researchers in developing, testing, training, hosting, and operating AI-based image analysis services, following FAIR practices.
- **Five operational and three prototype AI-based image analysis services** with image repositories will be developed and deployed at the iImagine AI platform to provide open access and exploitation by researchers. They will also be instrumental in demonstrating value and fostering further uptake by a large community of target users and beneficiaries.
- **Best Practices** – consisting of documentation and training materials – will be compiled giving practical guidance and examples to end-users on exploiting image datasets and analysis applications offered by the iImagine portfolio and serving as an example to whoever wishes to develop and deliver similar AI-based image analysis services and image repositories.

The activities related to the Innovation and Exploitation Management in the iImagine project fall under task 2.1 with the main objectives to:

1. Implement and conduct an operational innovation management process.
2. Capture and assess project results for exploitation readiness.
3. Identify and articulate the Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
4. Organise hands-on workshops (for example, business models) that will support the innovation management and exploitation activities.
5. Monitor changing market landscapes, responding to feedback and the potential for new business opportunities.
6. Provide facilitation in project events and meetings (for example, brainstorming sessions).

Purpose of the document

The purpose of the document is to draw some starting guidelines, identify processes, introduce key concepts and tools, formulate templates, and structure activities so as to drive the innovation management and exploitation activities in iImagine. This document

refers to the target groups as identified in the D2.1 First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement plan for the exploitation purposes.

Scope of the document

The first iteration of this deliverable covers Innovation Management and Exploitation aspects mainly focused on the project results and KERs. The second iteration of this public document will also cover the plan for business modelling and sustainability analysis. The outcome of the business modelling and sustainability analysis, however, will be included in the D2.6 (Business Model analysis and Sustainability Plan) which will be marked as sensitive. The final iteration of the deliverable will focus on showcasing the outputs of innovation management and exploitation activities and lessons learned during the project.

Structure of the document

The proceeding sections follow the following structure,

- Next section provides an overview of the various activities which fall under the innovation and exploitation management.
- A section is then dedicated to each of these activities.
- Finally, the last section provides the focus for the first year of the project.

Innovation and Exploitation Activities

Innovation and Exploitation Management approach of the iMagine project derives loosely from the Technology Management Process¹ and ISO 56002:2019 Innovation management – Innovation management system – Guidance². However, both these approaches are geared towards organisations. So the elements from these approaches are modified to better suit the requirements of a Horizon Europe project. Innovation and Exploitation management in a Horizon Europe project should cover the following aspects:

1. Managing the IP and its rights related to the project (Background, Sideground, Third-party and Foreground).
2. Capturing and managing information related to the results developed by the project.
3. Developing a comprehensive business plan/case for the project results.
4. Developing exploitation strategies and documenting exploitation, impact and success stories originating from the project.

¹ Gregory, M.J. (1995), "Technology management: a process approach", Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Vol. 209, pp. 347–56.

² <https://www.iso.org/standard/68221.html>

Using all of these as a basis following activities were identified that needed to be carried out by T2.1:

- Stakeholder Analysis
- Key Exploitable Result Management
- Project Result Management
- Intellectual Property Management
- Business Modelling and Sustainability Analysis
- Exploitation Strategy
- Impact Analysis

Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder analysis is the process of collecting information about any person that will be impacted by (or can impact) your project. Conducting a stakeholder analysis will enable you to identify all your stakeholders as well as their needs and expectations. The goals of this activity are to,

1. Identify and map stakeholders relevant to the iMagine project.
2. Assess stakeholder engagement and awareness.
3. If required, identify ways to improve stakeholder engagement and awareness.

Stakeholder identification

As mentioned earlier, this deliverable will build on the target group mapping done in D2.1 to develop the stakeholder analysis. As part of this activity, the identified target groups will be mapped against the stakeholder groups as defined in the Horizon Result Platform.

Stakeholder Engagement Assessment Matrix

Once the stakeholder groups are mapped, they will be assessed intermittently using the SEAM. The SEAM supports the comparison between the current engagement levels of stakeholders and the desired engagement levels required. This assessment will feed into the communication and dissemination strategy by helping in determining who to engage with, how to engage them, and what kind of information or resources they may need. The engagement will be gauged at five levels as suggested in the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK) guide³,

1. Unaware — Not aware of the project or its impact
2. Resistant — Aware of the project but resistant to change
3. Neutral — Aware of the project, but neither supportive nor resistant
4. Supportive — Aware and supportive of the project

³ <https://www.pmi.org/pmbok-guide-standards>

5. Leading — Aware of and actively engaged in ensuring the success of the project

Following figure provides an example⁴ of a stakeholder engagement assessment matrix with desired (“D”) and current (“C”) levels of engagement per stakeholder.

Stakeholder	Unaware	Resistant	Neutral	Supportive	Leading
Stakeholder 1	C			D	
Stakeholder 2			C	D	
Stakeholder 3				D C	
...					
Stakeholder n					

Stakeholder prioritisation

The last part of the stakeholder analysis prioritises the identified stakeholders. Since it’s likely the project will not be able to meet the needs of all stakeholders at the same time, prioritising is a good strategy to get your engagement started.

If required, the stakeholders will be prioritised with the support of the Activity and Service Board. Once the stakeholders are prioritised, ways to engage that specific stakeholder group may be brainstormed.

Key Exploitable Result management

A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is a project result or a group of similar project results with particularly high exploitation potential, i.e. use and benefits from something often for commercial purposes or in public policymaking or for further research. The goals of this activity are to,

1. Identify and manage KERs.
2. Identify KER Ambassadors.
3. Collect information related to KERs.

During the iImagine proposal phase, five KERs were identified, all of which are an umbrella under which two or more project results are grouped. It is possible that during the

⁴ <https://project-management.info/stakeholder-engagement-matrix/>

execution of the project, additional KERs may be identified. The five KERs defined during the proposal phase were,

1. A portfolio of proven, operational, AI services available to the relevant domain researchers and the wider EOSC and AI4EU user communities (KER1).
2. A portfolio of new AI services that have been technologically validated in the relevant environments, which would be further developed after the project (KER2).
3. A large collection of high-quality image repositories (KER3).
4. iImagine framework for developing, testing, training, deploying, and running AI-based models and imaging applications (KER4).
5. Lessons learnt and best practice documentation for adoption and deployment of AI in image analysis services (KER5).

A key aspect of the Horizon Europe projects is that every KER should be submitted to the Horizon Results Platform (HRP). The template for the HRP, though extensive, still misses some of the important aspects. So the HRP template has been expanded to cover these aspects so that all the relevant information for each KER is captured in the same place. The extended template for KERs, along with explanatory notes, can be found in the [iImagine confluence](#)⁵.

KER Ambassadors

Collecting the information in the template will be done in collaboration with the KER Ambassador. For each of the KERs identified, one or two KER Ambassadors will be appointed with the support of the iImagine Activity and Service Board (ASB). These KER Ambassadors, together with the Innovation Manager leading, will form the Innovation and Exploitation Group (IEG) of the iImagine project.

KER Ambassadors have the following role in the project,

1. They will act as an Ambassador for the KER – a primary spokesperson within the project, helping to encourage uptake, exploitation and dissemination of the KER.
2. They will provide the relevant data for the Horizon Result Platform template for their respective KERs.
3. They will support the development and exploitation plan, pointing to the relevant contact persons for technical, IP and other exploitation plan aspects of the KER.
4. They will take the lead in providing inputs on dissemination messaging.
5. They will also help bridge the gap between technical outputs and their practical implications by promoting uptake.

⁵ <https://confluence.egi.eu/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=139493552>

Project Result Management

A project result is any output generated during the project implementation. Some examples of project results include know-how, experience, algorithms, prototypes, new products or services, policy recommendations, roadmaps, learnings, reports, publications, data, events, etc. The goals of this activity are to,

- Identify, record and manage the project results.
- Curate detailed information for a subset of the project results.
- Ensure that innovation developed or enhanced by the project is well-documented.

This activity will capture all the results generated during the project duration on this [confluence page](#)⁶. Though all project results are captured and documented, detailed analysis will be limited to a subset of the results which fall under the umbrella of a KER. The detailed project result template with explanatory notes can be found here on this [confluence page](#)⁷.

Intellectual Property Management

This activity documents and manages the intellectual property that existed before the project started (relevant to the execution and exploitation of the project) and will be generated during the project duration. The goals of this activity are to,

1. Identify, record and manage the Background IP, Third-party IP and Sideground IP.
2. Ensure sufficient rights exist to the Background, Third-party and Sideground IP.
3. Identify and record the Foreground IP.
4. Protect the Foreground IP using appropriate methods and support resolution of any IP conflicts that may arise.
5. Develop any agreements related to the generated IP (joint ownership, licensing, etc.)

There are four types of intellectual property in the context of the iMagine project that could be relevant,

1. Background IP is generally identified as part of the Consortium Agreement writing phase before the project starts. Background IP will be documented here on [this page](#)⁸.
2. Sideground IP is captured during the project execution phase with the collaboration of the partners. Sidegroup IP will be documented here on [this page](#)⁹.

⁶ <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/IMP/Catalogue+of+Project+Results>

⁷ <https://confluence.egi.eu/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=139493554>

⁸ <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/IMP/Background+IP>

⁹ <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/IMP/Sideground+IP>

3. Third-party IP is captured during the project execution phase with the collaboration of the partners. Third-party IP will be documented here on [this page](#)¹⁰.
4. Foreground IP is captured during the execution of the project and is important to ensure that sufficient rights exist to ensure the successful exploitation of the project results to which this IP is connected. There might be multiple foreground IP that is connected to each project result, or the generated foreground IP may be connected to multiple project results. Foreground IP will be documented here on [this page](#)¹¹.

Business Modelling and Sustainability Analysis

Task 2.1 will organise a business modelling workshop for all the use cases involved in the project. This workshop will be based on the Business Model Navigator¹² approach blended in with elements of Business Model Canvas¹³ and Lean Canvas¹⁴. However, the business model will be represented with a graphical approach as compared to the traditional canvas to better convey the information. The outline of this workshop along with an updated plan for this analysis will be presented in the update of this deliverable (D2.5 Innovation Management and Exploitation Updated Plan). The output of this workshop will be presented in the D2.6 Business Model analysis and Sustainability Plan.

The goal of this activity will be to,

1. Conduct business model workshops for all
2. Develop business models for all the use cases
3. Describe sustainability plans for all the iMagine KERs

Exploitation Strategy

The goals of this activity are to,

1. Collect partner-specific exploitation plans
2. Develop a collective exploitation strategy

The activity is strongly linked and supported by the Key Exploitable Result Management and the Business Modelling and Sustainability Analysis activities. The KER Management activity will collect all the relevant information, including but not limited to value

¹⁰ <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/IMP/Third-party+IP>

¹¹ <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/IMP/Foreground+IP>

¹² <https://businessmodelnavigator.com/>

¹³ <https://www.strategyzer.com/canvas/business-model-canvas>

¹⁴ <https://leanstack.com/lean-canvas>

proposition, target groups, background information, etc in a single template which will streamline exploitation planning. The Business Modelling and Sustainability Analysis on the other hand will look into making the results available beyond the project for exploitation purposes. All this information will be combined with the individual exploitation plans from each partner to develop a collective exploitation strategy at the end of the project.

Individual exploitation plans from each partner will be collected in the [following template included in the iImagine confluence](#)¹⁵. The plan for developing an exploitation strategy will be further expanded upon in the next update of this deliverable.

Impact Analysis

In the long term, the results of the iImagine project are expected to contribute strongly towards the aquatic sciences and accelerate progress towards healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters. Therefore, it is important to better understand and disseminate and communicate the impact of the project to all its relevant stakeholders. The goals of this activity will therefore be to,

1. Support all workpackages in capturing the impact of their activities.
2. Support T2.2 in communicating this impact in the form of success stories, recommendations, best practices, etc.

This activity will have a strong linkage with all other work packages and tasks in the project.

Plan for the next 15 months

This plan will be updated in M21. Until then, the focus will be on collecting information for the various templates mentioned earlier. To begin with, KER Ambassadors will be appointed with the support of the ASB, who together will form the IEG. With the support of this IEG, the first version of the filled project result templates and the KER templates will be generated. These templates will be reviewed periodically with the same group. T 2.1 will support to perform the stakeholder analysis to better target the dissemination and communication activities. The background IP will be documented based on the background declared in the CA. Finally, the outline of the business modelling workshop will be developed.

¹⁵ <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/IMP/Exploitation+Plans>

Acronyms

AI Artificial Intelligence

ASB Activity and Service Board

CA Consortium Agreement

IEG Innovation and Exploitation Group

RI Research Infrastructures

AI4EU (project) AI on-demand platform to support research excellence in Europe

EOSC European Open Science Cloud

KER Key Exploitable Result

NGO Non-governmental organisation

SEAM Stakeholder Engagement Assessment Matrix